

Dialectic of Consciousness and Unconsciousness

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 04 Sep 2024; **Accepted:** 04 Oct 2024; **Published:** 08 Nov 2024

Abstract: Consciousness and unconsciousness play an important role in human life and psychology. The relationship between these two concepts and their dialectic defines human thinking, emotions and social relations.

This article focuses on the study of the dialectic of consciousness and unconsciousness. Consciousness refers to a person's ability to be aware of himself, manage his emotions, and understand his environment. Unconsciousness means that a person performs his activities without knowing. The relationship between these two concepts and their dialectic is important in human psychology, as well as in social and cultural processes.

Keywords: Consciousness, Unconsciousness, Dialectic, Psychology, thinking, being, Social relations, man, self-awareness, understanding, awareness.

This topic is one of the important issues that determine human thinking, emotions and social relations. Understanding the relationship between consciousness and unconsciousness allows for a deeper understanding of the inner and outer world of humanity. Consciousness is a person's ability to self-awareness, understand the environment and manage emotions. In conscious states, a person is clearly aware of his thoughts and decisions. Conscious thoughts and decisions take an important place in psychology. Unconsciousness is a person's actions without knowing it. In this process, a person often acts automatically or intuitively. In the psychoanalytical theory of Z. Freud, the unconscious reveals human internal conflicts and processes of repression. Dialectic is the process of interaction and development between ideas and concepts. Hegel's dialectic examines the relationship between consciousness and the unconscious. They are interdependent and complement each other. Marx emphasizes the influence of consciousness and unconsciousness in the social context. Studying the dialectical relationship between consciousness and unconsciousness helps to better understand the inner and social life of a person. These concepts complement each other and reveal the complexity of human thinking.

Consciousness is the ability of a person to understand his inner world, feelings and thoughts. It is important for personal development and self-knowledge. Conscious states facilitate creative thinking and generating new ideas. Creativity often depends on conscious processes. Consciousness is an important determinant of human social relations. Self-awareness and understanding of others deepens social interactions. It offers different approaches to the study of consciousness, for example, Descartes' idea that "I think, therefore I go" emphasizes the existence of consciousness. Mind plays a central role in human life and its development affects personal and social development.

Unconsciousness represents a person's ignorance of needs, feelings and thoughts in relation to the environment and his inner state. Unconscious states can create random human behavior or automatic reactions. Consciousness and unconsciousness play an important role in human life and psychology. Consciousness improves a person's attitude to himself and the environment, and unconsciousness can cause many problems. Each person's desire to develop his consciousness helps to improve the quality of his life.

Dialectic of the unconscious is the process of studying the relationship between conscious and unconscious states. This concept refers to the interaction between consciousness and unconsciousness in human thinking and social relations, the process of their development. The dialectic of unconsciousness is also seen in the social context. People are influenced by social environment, culture and upbringing, which causes them to make conscious or unconscious decisions. For example, social pressure or norms can make it difficult for a person to be aware of his own behavior. Understanding the unconscious is an important step in personal development. When the states of the unconscious are studied, a person can identify his internal problems and strive to eliminate them. This process leads to self-awareness and the development of consciousness. The dialectic of the unconscious is an important tool for understanding the complex processes of human thinking. The interaction between consciousness and unconsciousness plays an important role in shaping human self-awareness, development and social relations. This understanding can help people to resolve conflicts in their lives and develop themselves.

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